

PEDAGOGICAL INQUIRY ON PHYSICAL EDUCATION USING BLENDED ONLINE MODALITY: A COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 9

Pages: 999-1012

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1825

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11195723

Manuscript Accepted: 04-15-2024

Pedagogical Inquiry on Physical Education using Blended Online Modality: A Comparative Assessment

Pedrito M. Castillo II,* Marmee Rochelle M. Potenciando, Glydale John G. Escabarte

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The main aim of the study is to evaluate the quality of PE teaching and learning as well as determine the experiences of students in the PE blended-online delivery mode. Utilizing both quantitative and qualitative research methods, where a purposive sample of 1456 GPE 3 and 4 students participated in an online survey via Google form. The statistical treatment was done using Mean, Paired T-test and Pearson r. The results revealed that the PE students are generally satisfied with the quality of PE teaching and learning during the shift to blended-online delivery mode amidst the COVID-19 pandemic both in the main and branches. Students have demonstrated commendable levels of learning outcomes or competencies in PE knowledge, skills and behaviors. However, when the in-depth interview results were coded and categorized into themes, the respondents raised opportunities for improvement to further enhance the quality of PE teaching and learning. Teachers are also worthy of being asked not just about the quality of instruction but also about their struggles during the blended-online delivery mode.

Keywords: *physical education, learning outcomes, assessment, instruction PE teachers*

Introduction

Throughout the world, the Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) pandemic has profoundly affected the quality of teaching and learning across academic programs and courses. In particular, physical education (PE) has undergone significant changes as a result of the health crisis and advancement in digital technology, moving from face-to-face instruction to hybrid or online instruction (Nie, 2020; Thais, 2020; Thai, 2022). However, the shift has been hounded by challenges in terms of academic integrity, student readiness, motivation, retention, and technology challenges (Domokos et al., 2020). More importantly, challenges such as teaching motor abilities, athletic skills, dancing, and fitness, as well as ensuring students' social and emotional growth (Filiz & Konukman, 2020), likewise questioned the quality of PE teaching and learning.

Moreover, the higher education institutions and PE teachers were plagued with poor IT infrastructure (Chan et al., 2021; Thais, 2020), relatively relevant professional development activities for teaching and non-teaching staff, technological incompetence of personnel (Boyer-Davis, 2020; Mocanu, Murariu, Iordan, Sandu, & Mihaela Orlanda, 2021), and rigidity of instructional resources (Pedgley, Rognoli & Karana, 2016). The COVID-19 health crisis has tremendously challenged the quality of predominantly online teaching and learning PE classes (Lau & Lee, 2020) among higher education institutions worldwide. Online PE classes have faced numerous difficulties, such as unstable internet connection or technical problems (Wang et al., 2020), which caused unnecessary instructional delays, technological incompetence of students, teachers, and staff (Zhang et al., 2020) in the use of learning management system, open technologies and apps which caused stress and lack of interaction between students and teachers during classes, and the failure of some schools to smoothly transition from face-to-face instruction to online delivery mode (Adedoyin & Soykan, 2020).

However, studies during the COVID-19 pandemic revealed that the shift to online PE classes had reported both negative and positive results regarding teaching and learning quality. PE teachers' reluctance to employ teaching methods and assessments in online classes has hampered students' skills acquisition and training (Zhang et al., 2020). This can be attributed to the increase in teachers' workload not to mention the need to revise the PE curriculum and lesson preparation (Rizwan et al., 2021). The curriculum restructuring and lesson preparation should underscore creativity and active engagement to sustain students' motivation and interest (Lau & Lee, 2020).

On the other hand, Zheng, Yu-Yu, and Hung-Lung (2021) reported that online learning has helped students understand the PE basic concepts, perform the competencies, and realize key fitness knowledge (Rizwan et al., 2021) and improved active participation (Hussein, Daoud, Alrabaiah & Badawi, 2020). In support, Hrehorowicz (2021) and Badaru, Juhannis, and Hasmyati (2021) revealed that the majority of the students are satisfied with how the online PE classes are structured and their effectiveness, have expressed sincere intention to maximize the synchronous virtual sessions (Zheng et al., 2021) but reported students gaining weight during the health crisis (Rizwan et al., 2021). Moreover, Kwang-Jin, Noh, and Keun-Ok (2021) reported that the synchronous online class positively affected students' health and skill-related fitness components and competencies.

The extant PE research would empirically inform the value of regular physical classes and activities during the health crisis (Promoting Physical Activity, 2020). While the country is enslaved with stringent health and community quarantine protocols (DOH, 2020), higher education institutions should ensure that their students continue to do regular physical activity routines. The lack of opportunities for students to release their exuberant energy, coupled with the anxiety and loneliness that the pandemic brings, has resulted in an alarming rise in suicide (Pathare et al., 2020) and depression cases among students (Jane, Biswas & Perreira, 2021; Mocanu et al., 2021). Thus, higher education institutions should ensure that PE teaching and learning quality continues despite the pandemic.

In the same vein, the shift to multi-modal and other flexible learning modes during the health crisis does not only challenge the school's IT infrastructure and capability, but it has also caused unnecessary technostress to both teachers and students (Booker, Rebman &

Kitchens, 2014; Wang, Seng & Lu, 2020). Many teachers, particularly the baby boomers, are reluctant and relatively ignorant of the use of different technology tools (computer desktop, laptop, smartphones, iPod, tablet) and open educational resources and technologies (YouTube, SNS, OER, open access tools, teaching apps) in teaching and learning (Wang et al., 2020). Because of the sudden shift to flexible learning modes, teachers were expediently required to learn to navigate and utilize the said technology tools (Pallavi & Vrinda, 2021) and become experts in learning management systems (Booker et al., 2014). Similarly, while the students of this generation are technologically inclined (Shakeel & Bhatti, 2020), a significant few still struggles to adjust to remote teaching and learning, particularly in the use of LMS (Shakeel & Bhatti, 2020; The influence of digital tools, 2021) not to mention the very unstable access to the internet. For PE teachers, where competency demonstration is a common teaching strategy, the new normal of teaching and learning is undeniably challenging.

This study is anchored on the proposition of Aragon (2003) and Glickman (2003), who argued that online instruction that has no substantive and meaningful interaction, coupled with a poor sense of presence, contributes to a sense of isolation, unsatisfying learning experiences, and high dropout rates of students. Moreover, the investigation is guided by the constructive alignment theory of Biggs (2003), who posited that learning outcomes or competencies should dictate teachers' assessment and instructional design. In relation, Schulmann (1987) emphatically argued that quality teachers should possess a reasonable competence in content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge, pedagogical content knowledge, and technological content knowledge.

The need to continue offering PE classes during the health crisis is undoubtedly very important. However, the most recent literature reveals that there is a dearth of research relative to the quality of teaching and learning of PE (Pallavi & Vrinda, 2021), particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic (Boyer-Davis, 2020) at the higher education level (Rizwan et al., 2021) in a flexible or blended-online delivery mode. Thus, the researchers who are PE teachers themselves are challenged to fill in the identified research gap.

Research Objectives

The study's main objective is to determine the quality of teaching and learning in PE classes before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, it sought to:

1. To determine the quality of PE teaching and learning before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of:
 - 1.1. learning outcomes/competencies,
 - 1.2. teaching-learning activities/tasks,
 - 1.3. learning environment, and
 - 1.4. global quality and learning.
2. To determine students' quality of learning before and during the online delivery for main and branches in terms of:
 - 2.1. cognitive,
 - 2.2. behavioral, and
 - 2.3. skills.
3. To determine the difference between the main and branches' quality of teaching and learning before and during the COVID-19 pandemic.
4. To describe students' experiences in the blended-online PE delivery mode.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilizes quantitative and qualitative research methods to determine the pedagogical quality of PE in the blended-online instructional mode.

Participants

A purposive sample of 1,456 General Physical Education (GPE) 3 and 4 students officially enrolled in the main and branches of the University of Mindanao for two (2) consecutive semesters of the school year 2021 – 2022 were the participants of the study. A purposive sample is one whose characteristics are established for a goal pertinent to the investigation (Andrade, 2021). For the experiences of students in regard to the blended online delivery mode, eight (8) officially enrolled students participated in the semi-structured interview. Excluded in the study were GPE 3 and 4 students enrolled only for a semester in the said school year, as well as GPE 1 and 2 students.

Instruments

This study utilized both quantitative non-experimental, and qualitative methods of research. For the quantitative method, the researchers have developed a survey questionnaire for the quality of PE teaching based on the outcome-based education (OBE) framework and John Bigg's constructive alignment theory (2003). It was validated by experts with a mean score of 4.30 and a description of very high. For the quality of learning, the study utilized Spady's (1988) framework and operational definition of learning outcomes which refers to the intended knowledge, skills, and behaviors that students should demonstrate upon completion of a course. Moreover, the

researchers utilized the class records of PE teachers of the previous two semesters of the school year 2021-2022, where the survey participants were likewise enrolled. A Five-Likert scale was used to assess students' responses on the quality of teaching and learning in the physical education questionnaire.

Table 1. *The 5-point Scale, its Mean range, and interpretation*

<i>Mean Interval</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.21-5.00	Very High	Satisfaction is always evident.
3.41-4.20	High	Satisfaction is oftentimes evident.
2.61-3.40	Moderate	Satisfaction is sometimes evident.
1.81-2.60	Low	Satisfaction is seldom evident.
1.00-1.80	Very Low	Satisfaction is not evident

Procedure

In the quantitative method, the researchers administered a questionnaire on the quality of teaching and learning in physical education. Quantitative methods either assist in the discovery of actual facts or the development of the explanatory theory (Haig, 2018) to comprehend the outside world as it "really" is (Schutt, 2019). On the other hand, the qualitative method in this study is used to supplement the result of the data analysis of the questionnaire to get in-depth insight from the respondents regarding their experiences in the blended-online instructional mode of their PE classes. A qualitative method is important for comprehending complicated concerns and social processes that underlie the study of specific phenomena (Behling, Lenzi & Rossetto, 2022).

Relative to the gathering of data, the researchers sought approval from the academic affairs office of the University of Mindanao to conduct the study. The approval was sent to the university records and admission center to have access to the previous class records of teachers' and students' grades. The questionnaire was administered through an anonymous online survey via Google form from December 2021 to February 2022. Prior to filling in the survey and interview, participants were asked to read the instructions of the study. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants through the online survey. This was when almost all of the higher education institutions were closed in all parts of the country. Second, the researchers conducted a semi-structured interview with selected participants to share their experiences with the blended-online delivery mode. Next, the researchers gathered and analyzed the qualitative data thematically, while the quantitative data were subjected to statistical analysis.

Ethical Considerations

There are considerable ethical issues and concerns that have specifications for the quantitative inquest. Such issues and concerns may arise primarily from the methodology involved in this study. The ethical contests that are pertinent to this research concern the issues of the right to conduct the study, confidentiality and anonymity.

The researcher will observe and follows full ethical standards in the conduct of the study following the protocol assessments and standardized criteria, particularly in managing the population and data such as, but not limited to:

Voluntary Participation. Each participant should participate voluntarily and under no duress, with no penalty or consequence being impressed upon their cooperation. Only after presenting the benefits and purpose of the study they will be asked to participate, with their rights and privileges as free participants upheld all throughout.

Privacy and confidentiality. Each participant will be given the option of anonymity and given their right to privacy. All data contained within this study is therefore displayed with their connections under strict confidentiality.

Informed consent process. Absolute clarity will be provided for by the researcher, with the purpose and wording of the study and questionnaire being open for inquiry should the participant request it. All reasonable measures to remain transparent during the administration of data collection will be observed.

Recruitment. Distribution, data collection, and administration procedures are all included within the study's parameters, including the number and manner of respondents involved in the study.

Risks. Research parameters are limited to the absolute minimum risk for mental or psychological damage. All questions and methodologies are adapted to present the least amount of inconvenience and disruption.

Benefits. All participants will be given an in-depth explanation of the outcome of the study, and a copy of the research outcome if they requested it. Information relevant to the operations of the institution will be provided on request.

Plagiarism. No content contained within the study is misrepresentative of someone else's views, and the body of the research will undergo plagiarism checking with third-party tools.

Fabrication. The study contains no fabrications pertaining to data, opinion, or citation. All references are provided with links and DOI coding for the purpose of fact-checking.

Falsification. No falsehoods are made in order to represent another, and all data can be verified using the methodologies and limitations

stipulated over the course of the study.

Conflict of interest (COI). No other interest aside from the pursuit of honest truth is represented by this study, nor is it sponsored in any way by third-party individuals in order to present misleading results.

Deceit. The study aims to be completely transparent in its conduct, and no participants will be misled to believe anything outside its stipulated purpose.

Authorship. The researchers of this study are faculty from the College of Teacher Education of the University of Mindanao. The researchers of the study will undergo a series of content revisions following suggestions and modifications put forward by their research adviser

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the assessment of the quality of teaching and learning of PE blended-online classes and students' experiences of the said instructional delivery during the advent of the COVID-19 health crisis.

Table 1. *Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of learning outcomes/competencies*

	<i>Before COVID-19</i>				<i>During COVID-19</i>			
	<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>		<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
1. Clearly explaining the expected learning outcomes or competencies that will be performed after completing the subject.	4.62	0.69	4.60	0.59	4.50	0.71	4.27	0.74
2. Clearly explaining the importance of learning competencies to one's career and life in general.	4.59	0.67	4.62	0.56	4.53	0.68	4.41	0.74
3. Ensuring that the leaning competencies or outcomes of the subject while challenging, can be completed based on the time duration of the subject.	4.58	0.69	4.64	0.57	4.52	0.69	4.31	0.73
4. Ensuring that the stated learning competencies or outcomes are clear and understandable.	4.64	0.66	4.66	0.55	4.59	0.66	4.42	0.69
Overall	4.61	0.61	4.63	0.48	4.54	0.61	4.35	0.62
Mean Before COVID-19: 4.61	SD: 0.60				Outstanding			
Mean During COVID-19: 4.52	SD: 0.61				Outstanding			

Table 1.2. *Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of teaching-learning activities/tasks*

	<i>Before COVID-19</i>				<i>During COVID-19</i>			
	<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>		<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
1. Using varied and appropriate teaching strategies that will help perform the major exams or assessment tasks.	4.61	0.68	4.60	0.56	4.52	0.71	4.35	0.70
2. Using appropriate technology tools (Power Point, Excel, Videos, Adobe, YouTube, Ted.com) to perform the major exams or assessment tasks.	4.48	0.79	4.53	0.72	4.63	0.65	4.53	0.62
3. Conducting teaching-learning activities to deeply understand the subject content.	4.60	0.68	4.64	0.54	4.54	0.68	4.40	0.74
4. Always well-prepared in the conduct of teaching-learning activities.	4.59	0.70	4.66	0.53	4.58	0.68	4.45	0.65
5. Conducting teaching-learning activities that are related to the learning competencies or outcomes.	4.64	0.65	4.63	0.61	4.60	0.66	4.44	0.65
6. Conducting teaching-learning activities in preparation for highly graded performances or exams.	4.65	0.65	4.68	0.54	4.61	0.66	4.48	0.65
Overall	4.60	0.61	4.62	0.48	4.58	0.59	4.44	0.57
Mean Before COVID-19: 4.60	SD: 0.60				Outstanding			
Mean During COVID-19: 4.57	SD: 0.59				Outstanding			

Table 1.3. *Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of assessment of learning*

	<i>Before COVID-19</i>				<i>During COVID-19</i>			
	<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>		<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
1. Conducting activities or exercises that are related to the major exams or performances of the subject.	4.63	0.67	4.69	0.55	4.61	0.65	4.50	0.66
2. Ensuring that the schedule, coverage and type of exam in the subject are given before the start of classes.	4.62	0.68	4.64	0.59	4.64	0.66	4.43	0.70

3. Designing major exams that are fair and appropriate.	4.63	0.68	4.66	0.51	4.60	0.66	4.49	0.63
4. Designing major exams that measures the achievement of learning competencies or outcomes of the subject.	4.61	0.68	4.64	0.55	4.59	0.64	4.45	0.66
5. Providing timely constructive feedback about performance in activities and exercises and major exams or performances.	4.54	0.72	4.58	0.58	4.47	0.78	4.39	0.72
6. Clearly explaining the criteria on how performance tasks are assessed.	4.64	0.66	4.66	0.51	4.63	0.65	4.44	0.66
Overall	4.61	0.62	4.65	0.49	4.59	0.59	4.45	0.58
Mean Before COVID-19: 4.61	SD: 0.61				Outstanding			
Mean During COVID-19: 4.58	SD: 0.59				Outstanding			

Table 1.4. *Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of learning environment*

	<i>Before COVID-19</i>				<i>During COVID-19</i>			
	<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>		<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
1. Very helpful and easy to communicate with when there are difficulties in the subject.	4.59	0.70	4.68	0.54	4.50	0.75	4.33	0.80
2. Manifesting a very high sense of professionalism in dealing with students.	4.60	0.68	4.75	0.46	4.57	0.70	4.50	0.66
3. Encouraging to participate during class discussions or activities.	4.61	0.69	4.69	0.54	4.56	0.72	4.55	0.62
4. Allowing to voice out ideas and opinions about the subject content, major exams and activities or exercises.	4.59	0.69	4.65	0.55	4.56	0.70	4.53	0.65
5. Establishing an atmosphere where students are respected, recognized and valued.	4.65	0.65	4.71	0.49	4.63	0.66	4.54	0.62
Overall	4.61	0.63	4.69	0.45	4.57	0.63	4.49	0.58
Mean Before COVID-19: 4.61	SD: 0.62				Outstanding			
Mean During COVID-19: 4.56	SD: 0.63				Outstanding			

Table 1.5. *Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of global quality and learning standards*

	<i>Before COVID-19</i>				<i>During COVID-19</i>			
	<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>		<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
1. Conducting teaching-learning activities or exercises and major exams that require to think critically.	4.57	0.70	4.66	0.55	4.52	0.70	4.38	0.67
2. Conducting teaching-learning activities or exercises and major exams that require to further understand the values of gender equality and cultural awareness.	4.61	0.66	4.69	0.54	4.61	0.65	4.55	0.62
3. Integrating research findings (surveys, statistics, real data) and research articles to further enrich the lesson content.	4.42	0.80	4.53	0.66	4.40	0.78	4.33	0.74
4. Requiring the use technology tools or gadgets and resources in the demonstration of learning competencies or during teaching-learning activities and performances.	4.45	0.79	4.50	0.68	4.63	0.65	4.52	0.62
5. Requiring the use of problem-solving skills in the demonstration of learning competencies or during teaching-learning activities and performances.	4.46	0.76	4.56	0.62	4.43	0.75	4.42	0.66
6. Requiring to communicate effectively during the teaching-learning activities or with classmates.	4.59	0.69	4.61	0.56	4.51	0.74	4.41	0.71
7. Requiring to be creative during performance tasks.	4.63	0.68	4.65	0.50	4.66	0.63	4.56	0.65
8. Requiring to work with classmates to complete a performance task or activity.	4.60	0.72	4.64	0.55	4.32	0.92	4.34	0.86
Overall	4.54	0.63	4.60	0.47	4.51	0.60	4.44	0.57
Mean Before COVID-19: 4.55	SD: 0.62				Outstanding			
Mean During COVID-19: 4.50	SD: 0.60				Outstanding			

Table 1.6. *Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches*

	<i>Before COVID-19</i>				<i>During COVID-19</i>			
	<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>		<i>Main</i>		<i>Branches</i>	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Learning Outcomes/Competencies	4.61	0.61	4.63	0.48	4.54	0.61	4.35	0.62
Teaching-learning Activities/Tasks	4.60	0.61	4.62	0.48	4.58	0.59	4.44	0.57
Assessment of Learning	4.61	0.62	4.65	0.49	4.59	0.59	4.45	0.58

Learning Environment	4.61	0.63	4.69	0.45	4.57	0.63	4.49	0.58
Global Quality and Learning Standards	4.54	0.63	4.60	0.47	4.51	0.60	4.44	0.57
Overall QT	4.59	0.58	4.64	0.43	4.56	0.56	4.43	0.53
Mean Before COVID-19: 4.60	SD: 0.57			Outstanding				
Mean During COVID-19: 4.55	SD: 0.56			Outstanding				

Table 2.1. Quality of learning of students before COVID-19 on the online delivery for main and branches in terms of cognitive, behavioral, and skills

		Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Main	Cognitive	83	100	96	2.670
	Behavioral	75	100	99	2.925
	Skills	75	100	95	3.055
Branches	Cognitive	90	100	96	2.296
	Behavioral	90	100	100	1.265
	Skills	90	100	97	3.000
Mean: 97					Outstanding
SD: 1.753					

Table 2.2. Quality of learning of students during COVID-19 on the online delivery for main and branches in terms of cognitive, behavioral, and skills

		Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard Deviation
Main	Cognitive	15	100	94	4.669
	Behavioral	15	100	98	7.205
	Skills	15	100	90	11.919
Branches	Cognitive	83	100	95	3.043
	Behavioral	93	100	99	1.420
	Skills	66	100	93	6.338
Mean: 94					Very Satisfactory

Table 3.1. Significant difference between main and branches' quality of teaching and learning before COVID-19 pandemic

		Campus				
		Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
QTL Before Covid-19	Main	4.59	0.582	-0.800	0.424	Not Significant
	Branches	4.64	0.431			

Table 3.2. Significant difference between main and branches' quality of teaching and learning during COVID-19 pandemic

		Campus				
		Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
QTL During Covid-19	Main	4.56	0.558	2.206	0.028	Significant
	Branches	4.43	0.534			

Table 3.3. Significant difference between main and branches' quality of learning before COVID-19 pandemic

		Campus				
		Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
QL Before Covid-19	Main	96.75	1.767	-5.088	0.000	Significant

Table 3.4. Significant difference between main and branches' quality of learning during COVID-19 pandemic

		Campus				
		Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Interpretation
QL During Covid-19	Main	93.96	5.789	-2.988	0.003	Significant
	Branches	95.58	2.801			

Table 4. Significant relationship between quality of teaching and quality of learning before and during COVID-19

	<i>QL</i>				
	<i>r-value</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>r-squared</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
QTL	0.362	Moderate	0.131	0.01	Significant

Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of learning outcomes/competencies

As detailed in Table 1.1, the quality of teaching in terms of the expected Learning Outcomes/competencies that students should demonstrate upon completion of the course revealed a total mean rating of 4.61 (SD=0.61) and 4.63 (SD=0.48) for the UM main and branches respectively before the COVID-19 pandemic and 4.54 (SD=0.61) and 4.35 (SD=0.62) during the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, before the pandemic, the item ensuring that the stated learning competencies or outcomes were clear and understandable got the highest mean rating of 4.64 (SD=0.66) for the main and 4.66 (SD=0.55) for branches among all items in the table. The same is true during the pandemic, with a mean rating of 4.59 (SD=0.66) and 4.42 (SD=0.69) for the main and branches, respectively. The overall mean rating on the Quality of PE teaching before – 4.61 (SD=0.60) and during – 4.52 (SD=0.61) the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of learning outcomes/competencies were described as outstanding.

This implies that PE teachers were able to deliver the highest quality of teaching to students by explaining clearly the what, how, and why of the expected learning outcomes/competencies while ensuring that it can be realistically completed. According to Bertills et al. (2018), the quality of teaching is one factor in achieving learning outcomes. Quality of teaching is correlated with students' chances to take charge of their education and develop strong self-efficacy. The most effective teachers clearly convey high standards, and participate in individualized interactions to encourage each student's active participation in their learning and understanding.

Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of teaching-learning activities/tasks

Table 1.2 reflects the quality of PE teaching in regard to Teaching-Learning Activities/Tasks before and during the COVID-19 pandemic for the main and branches, respectively. As can be gleaned from the presentation, the said indicator got an overall mean rating of 4.60 (SD=0.61) and 4.62 (SD=0.48) before and 4.58 (0.59) and 4.44 (SD=0.57) during the COVID-19 pandemic for the main and branches respectively. For both main and branches before COVID-19 conducting teaching-learning activities in preparation for highly graded performances or exams got the highest mean value of 4.65 (SD=0.65) and 4.68 (SD=0.54), respectively. While during COVID-19 using appropriate technology tools (PowerPoint, Excel, Videos, Adobe, YouTube, Ted.com) to perform the major exams or assessment tasks got the highest mean value of 4.63 (SD=0.65) for main, and 4.53 (SD=0.62) for branches. The overall mean rating on the Quality of PE teaching before – 4.60 (SD=0.60) and during – 4.57 (SD=0.59) the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of teaching-learning activities/tasks were all described as outstanding.

Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of assessment of learning

As indicated in Table 1.3, the quality of teaching in terms of Assessment of Learning revealed a total mean rating of 4.61 (SD=0.62) and 4.65 (SD=0.49) for the UM main and branches, respectively, before the COVID-19 pandemic, and 4.59 (SD=0.59) and 4.45 (SD=0.58) during the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, before the pandemic, the item, clearly explaining the criteria on how performance tasks are assessed got the highest mean rating of 4.64 (SD=0.66) for main while conducting activities or exercises that are related to the major exams or performances of the subject got the highest mean rating of 4.69 (SD=0.55) for the branches. During the pandemic, ensuring that the schedule, coverage, and type of exam in the subject are given before the start of classes item got the highest mean rating of 4.64 (SD=0.66) for the main while for branches, the item is the same before the pandemic with a mean rating of 4.50 (SD=0.66). The overall mean rating on the Quality of PE teaching before – 4.61 (SD=0.61) and during – 4.58 (SD=0.59) the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of assessment of learning were all described as outstanding.

Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of learning environment

Table 1.4 shows the quality of PE teaching as regards to Learning Environment before and during the COVID-19 pandemic for the main and branches, respectively. As can be gleaned from the presentation, the said indicator got an overall mean rating of 4.61 (SD=0.63) and 4.69 (SD=0.45) before and 4.57 (0.63) and 4.49 (SD=0.58) during the COVID-19 pandemic for the main and branches respectively. Specifically, for main, the item, establishing an atmosphere where students are respected, recognized, and valued, got the highest mean rating of 4.65 (SD=0.65) and 4.63 (SD=0.66) before and during the pandemic, respectively. For branches, the item manifesting a very high sense of professionalism in dealing with students got the highest mean rating of 4.75 (SD=0.46) before the pandemic, while during the pandemic, the item encouraging to participate during class discussions or activities got the highest mean rating of 4.55 (SD=0.62). The overall mean rating on the Quality of PE teaching before – 4.61 (SD=0.62) and during – 4.56 (SD=0.63) the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of learning environment were all described as outstanding.

Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of global quality and learning standards

As indicated in Table 1.5, the quality of teaching in terms of Global Quality and Learning Standards revealed a total mean rating of 4.54 (SD=0.63) and 4.60 (SD=0.47) for the UM main and branches, respectively, before the COVID-19 pandemic, and 4.51 (SD=0.60)

and 4.44 (SD=0.57) during the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, for main, the item requiring creativity during performance tasks got the highest mean ratings of 4.63 (SD=0.68) and 4.66 (SD=0.63) before and during the pandemic, respectively. For branches, the item conducting teaching-learning activities or exercises and major exams that require further understanding of the values of gender equality and cultural awareness got the highest mean rating of 4.69 (SD=0.54) before the pandemic while during the pandemic, the item was the same with the main campus with 4.56 (SD=0.65) mean rating. The overall mean rating on the Quality of PE teaching before – 4.55 (SD=0.62) and during – 4.50 (SD=0.60) the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches in terms of global quality and learning standards were all described as outstanding.

Quality of PE teaching before and during the COVID-19 pandemic in the main and branches

Table 1.6 shows the overall mean rating for each of the indicators relative to the quality of PE teaching for the main and branches before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. The aforesaid variable revealed an overall mean rating of 4.59 (SD=0.58) and 4.64 (SD=0.43) before and 4.56 (SD=0.56) and 4.43 (SD=0.53) during the COVID-19 health crisis for the main and branches respectively. Among all the indicators, learning outcomes/competencies, assessment of learning, and learning environment got the highest mean rating of 4.61 for the main before COVID-19, while for the branches, the highest mean rating was 4.69 for the learning environment. During COVID-19, the assessment of learning got the highest mean rating of 4.59 for the main, and for the branches, the indicator with the highest mean rating is the same but with a 4.49 mean rating. The overall mean rating for the quality of PE teaching for main and branches including all its indicators were all described as outstanding with an overall mean rating of 4.60 (SD=0.57) and 4.55 (SD=0.56) before and during COVID-19 respectively. The results indicate that the PE students were extremely satisfied with the quality of teaching at the university before and during the COVID-19 pandemic for both main and branches. However, all the mean scores of the indicators decreased during the COVID-19 pandemic, including its overall mean rating.

Quality of learning of students before COVID-19 on the online delivery for main and branches in terms of cognitive, behavioral, and skills

Table 2.1 reveals the average grade of PE students in the cognitive, behavioral, and skills learning outcomes. As can be gleaned from the presentation, students' grades for both main (Cognitive – 96, SD= 2.670; Behavioral – 99, SD=2.925; Skills – 95, SD=3.055) and branches (Cognitive – 96, SD= 2.296; Behaviors – 100, SD=1.265; Skills – 97, SD=3.000) were outstanding respectively. Worthy of mentioning that PE students in the branches have a higher average grade than students on the main campus. Overall, the student's grades (M – 97, SD=1.753) are described as outstanding.

Quality of learning of students before COVID-19 on the online delivery for main and branches in terms of cognitive, behavioral, and skills

Detailed in Table 2.2 are the average grades of PE students in knowledge, behavioral, and skills learning outcomes during the COVID-19 pandemic. The data showed that the average grade of students in the branches (Cognitive – 95, SD= 3.043; Behavioral – 99, SD=1.420; Skills – 93, SD=6.338) are higher than the main campus (Cognitive – 94, SD= 4.669; Behavioral – 98, SD=7.205; Skills – 90, SD=11.919). Overall, the student's grades have decreased during the COVID-19 pandemic (M=94, SD=5.438), which is described as very satisfactory.

Significant difference between main and branches' quality of teaching and learning before COVID-19 pandemic

Presented in Table 3.1 is the significant difference between the main campus and branches as regards the quality of teaching and learning before the COVID-19 pandemic. The result showed no significant difference between the main campus (M=4.59, SD=0.582) and branches (M=4.64, SD=0.431) in the quality of teaching and before the COVID-19 pandemic with a t-value of 0.800, and p-value of 0.424 at 0.05 level of significance.

Significant difference between main and branches' quality of teaching and learning during COVID-19 pandemic

Presented in Table 3.2 is the significant difference between the main campus and branches as regards the quality of teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic. The result showed a significant difference between the main campus (M=4.56, SD=0.558) and branches (M=4.43, SD=0.534) in the quality of teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic with a t-value of 2.206, and the p-value is 0.028 at 0.05 level of significance.

Significant difference between main and branches' quality of learning during COVID-19 pandemic

Detailed in Table 3.3 is the significant difference between the main campus and branches as regards to quality of learning before the COVID-19 pandemic. The result showed that there was a significant difference between the main campus (M=96.75, SD=1.767) and branches (M=97.63, SD=1.282) in the quality of learning before the COVID-19 pandemic with a t-value of -5.088, and p-value of 0.000 at 0.05 level of significance.

Significant difference between main and branches' quality of learning during COVID-19 pandemic

Reflected in Table 3.4 is the significant difference between the main campus and branches as regards quality of learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The result showed that there was a significant difference between the main campus (M=93.96, SD=5.789) and

branches ($M=95.58$, $SD=2.801$) in the quality of learning during the COVID-19 pandemic; $t=-2.988$, $p=0.003$.

Significant relationship between quality of teaching and quality of learning before and during COVID-19

A Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient was computed to assess the relationship between the quality of teaching and quality of learning before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. There was a positive moderate correlation between the two variables, $r^2=0.131$, $p=0.01$. The satisfaction of students with the quality of teaching was correlated with increases in students' grades.

PE Students' Experience in the Blended-Online Delivery Mode

The thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews resulted in three major themes and several sub-themes. The major themes included: (1) knowledge of online learning; (2) challenges in running online physical education classes; and (3) opportunities for improvement in facilitating efficient and effective online physical education classes.

5.1 Knowledge about the Online Learning

The first theme that emerged from focus groups was the knowledge of participants about online learning and the role of online learning in physical education. This theme consisted of three sub-themes: (1) familiarity with online learning; (2) awareness of course content; and (3) difficulties in understanding course content.

5.1.1 Knowledge of Blended-Online Learning

Almost all participants were not knowledgeable about the blended-online learning delivery prior to the pandemic. Expectedly, all participants have never experienced PE classes through online learning. However, all participants have used digital and open technology tools, such as PE and sports-related recorded videos, apps, and social networking sites.

"Nadungog lang nako na online learning..., pero wala pa jud ko ka try ana... especially sa PE... sa PE man gud, nasanay jud mi nga actual jud ang pagperform"

I heard that it is online learning, but I have not tried it, especially in PE, because in PE, we were used to performing in an actual manner.

"In terms of technology, I think mas dali ra jud na sa amoa kay sanay man kaayu mi ana... sa paggamit ug tools, confident kayo ko nga dali lang sa akoa ang maka-learn kay exposed kaayu ko sa mga gadgets ug paggamit ug apps... mao nga pag abot sa LMS wala jud kaau ko naglisod kay dali ra man i-explore."

In terms of technology, it is easy for us because we are used to it. I am confident in using the tools and learning quickly since I am exposed to gadgets and apps, and the LMS is easy to explore.

"Na try ko na gumamit ng videos, apps, Microsoft office, Kahoot, Survey sa iba kong subjects, that is why hindi ako masyado nahirapan sa online learning. Problema lang talaga internet minsan... plus naa pa jud panahon na brownout."

I have no difficulty in online learning because I tried using videos, apps, Microsoft office, Kahoot, and Survey in my subjects. The problem is the internet connection and brownout.

5.1.2. Knowledge of Course Contents and Competencies

The next sub-theme has underscored the participants' knowledge and understanding of course content and competencies. The participants showed a commendable understanding of the course content and competencies in online learning mode, wherein a majority of participants agreed that PE classes could be delivered efficiently and effectively in blended-online learning.

"At first, akala ko talaga mahirapan kami sa activities naming sa PE kasi online, pero mas hayahay hinuon sa akoa kay mas taas among time maka practice sa mga performance tasks."

At first, I thought that I would have difficulty in my PE class online. Instead, it is more convenient since we have ample time for practice.

"Very clear kaayo ang mga instructions sa SIM [Self-Instructional Module], naa na didto jud tanan mao nga wala halos ko nag struggle."

I did not struggle much because the SIM (Self-Instructional Module) instruction was very clear.

"Sa blended-online mas naa mi chance maka pangita ug time nga according sa amoang comfort para mas ma deliver namu ang expectations sa amoa."

In the blended online, we have the chance to look for a convenient time to deliver what is expected of us.

"Pagdating sa mga performance tasks and LMS submissions, wala jud kayo ko naglisud kay naka declare na sa SIM tanan ang instructions how to do the tasks, the criteria, date of submission and performance pati pud and scoring [Rubrics]."

I do not have difficulty with performance tasks and LMS submission since all the instructions can be found in the SIM, like how to do

the tasks, criteria, due date, and rubrics.

All the participants are unanimous in saying that online learning provides them with opportunities to focus more on the topics and learning competencies. The participants have emphasized the value of recorded lectures, which they can watch again to further understand the content and competencies.

5.1.3. Personal Struggles in the Course

The next sub-theme emphasized the students' difficulties in the PE blended online course. While the participants have revealed less struggle in navigating and using technology tools, they struggled in terms of the learning environment and teachers' ability to respond to their learning needs. Some examples are given below:

"Makamingaw jud ang face to face... as in...lahi ra jud tong makita nimu in person ang mag clap or mag appreciate sa imuhang performance. Mahilig baya jud makipag socialize ang mga pinoy. Murag feeling nako walay naga tan-aw sa ako performance, mingaw kaayu."

I miss face to face; the feeling that you can see who appreciates my performance is satisfying, unlike online, as if nobody is watching me. Filipinos are fond of socializing.

"Pag naa man gud ang teacher ug imu classmates, lahi ra jud ang dating. Pag nag recite ako, di nako makita ang mga faces sa ako classmates ug teacher. Lisud makipag discuss sa ako mga classmate kay duda ko nagdaginot pud sila ug internet data, di parehas sa face to face, dali ra nimu sila ma storya."

The feeling is different when my teacher and classmates are around. I am hesitant to discuss because I feel that my classmates are saving internet data, unlike in face-to-face, they are easy to talk to.

"Usahay, dugay pud kaayu mag provide ug feedback akoang teacher sa ako performance ug submissions. Mao nga naga wonder pud ko kung ok ba kaha to ako performance. Importante kaayu ang comments or critiques sa teacher jud so that makabalo ko unsaon nako pag pasar sa subject."

Sometimes my teacher provides feedback late; it is important for me to be given feedback right away to be aware of my performance and do something to pass the subject.

"Para sa akin, ang school ug classroom atmosphere importante jud kaayu. Dami din kasi distractions sa online delivery like yung ingay ng kapitbahay and vendors pati dogs... sa school man gud kay nay library, pwede ka mag dula ug daghang areas nga maka hangout ka, pampawala ug stress."

School and classroom atmosphere is important for me; in an online class, distractions are there, like noises from the dogs, neighbors, etc., unlike in school, I can stay in the library, and I can relax because I can hang out and play with my friends.

5.2. Challenges Encountered Completing the PE Online Classes

The following section focuses on the participants who perceived challenges in completing their online PE class, namely limited spaces for physical activities, added weight due sedentary lifestyle during home quarantine, and psychological struggles such as depression and anxiety.

5.2.1. Impact on Performance in PE Tasks

Some of the participants of the study were profoundly disrupted by the lack of safe spaces where they could execute their performance tasks.

"PE classes are not the same with other subjects. Sa bahay kasi very halos walang space even sa subdivision because of quarantine and distancing protocols. Wala din facilities and equipment sa bahay obviously, kaya diskarte na lang jud. Maayo na lang kay very considerate pud kaayo amoang teacher..."

PE classes are not the same as the other subjects. At home, there's only a limited space even in subdivision areas due to quarantine protocols. There are also limited facilities and equipment in the house, so as a student you need to find some ways. And good to know that our teacher is very considerate with regards to that matter.

"At first nag doubt jud ko sa PE online class knowing nga kami ra jud mag practice on our own with very limited space, facilities or equipment. Samot na jud tong dili kaayo naga exercise parehas nako..."

At first, I have doubts about the PE online class knowing that we will be practicing alone the activity with very limited space, facilities, and equipment. Thus, the worst thing is that some of us are not into physical exercise.

"Kay limited man ang space ug equipment, ang amuang PE teacher mapugos na lang pud ug balik-balik ug lecture or kaya mag watch ug videos para lang naa jud mi buhaton..."

Since the space and equipment are limited, our PE teacher was forced to repeat the lecture and sometimes instructed us to watch videos for us to have work to do.

5.2.2. Weight Gain

Some of the participants of the study have gained weight due to physical inactivity during the advent of the COVID-19 epidemic. According to one of the participants, college students have growing problems with weight gain or poor lifestyle and psychological problems such as depression and anxiety during the pandemic; she further added that:

"Nag sige na lang ko ug kaun sa balay kay wala man lain mabuhat. Di rin ako makalabas kay bawal pud; strikto kaayu amo barangay. Maski naa koy PE class limitado lang man pud akoo mabuhat kay daghan kaayo bawal..."

I did overeat since there was nothing else to do and I cannot go out because of the strict protocol of the barangay. Even though there is a PE class, things are still limited due to strict protocols.

"Dili jud lalim ang pandemic sir, grabe jud, kung ang uban nasobrahan ug kaun, ako many times nga mag sige na lang ko ug tanga kanang wa na lang ka kabalo nga natulala na ka...Kaun, tulog, limpyo balay, online class, kaun n apud, di nako ma explain ang ka boring jud sa life. Maayo na lang level 2 na ang Davao, nakagawas na jud mi sa balay pero dili jud ko allowed sa akong parents mag laag..."

Experiencing a pandemic is not easy, I overeat and sometimes I cannot think of what things to do. I just did the same routine such as overeating, sleeping, doing household chores, and attending online classes and sometimes I feel bored. Fortunately, Davao City is now on level 2, at least this time we can go out and be allowed to do things outside our house.

5.2.3. Psychological Issues

One of the participants of the study stated that the online classes and health protocols have led to psychological issues. She further said:

"During the online classes, sometimes mag sabay-sabay ang mga deadlines, maka taranta pud. Na apud jud ubang teachers nga dili jud mo consider maski naa kay valid reason. Mudungag pa jud ang problem sa balay kay silingan namu nag COVID man unya namatay. Grabe kaayo ang stress ato nga time kay what if mahitabo sa akoo or sa ako mga igsuon or parents..."

During online classes, some of the activities have the same deadlines, and that makes me panic sometimes. Some teachers are not considerate even if you have a valid reason. There were a lot of problems as well during the pandemic and my anxiety was triggered as our neighbor died because of COVID-19. I feel stressed about overthinking things because of the pandemic.

"Tungod sa pagpondo sa balay for almost 2 years plus walay regular workout, unya wala baya jud ko naga workout, nisamot jud ang mga worries ug anxieties. Labin a tong nahitabo sa India nga ang mga tao nangamatay sa gawas sa hospital unya gisunog nga mura lang ug hayop, maka trauma jud. Diri sa Davao, puno ang mga hospital mao nga mag sige ra jud jud ka huna-huna unsaon nga dili ka masakit..."

Because of the very strict health protocol and staying-at-home protocol, I did not perform my regular workout, and since I don't have the avenue to do such things, the level of my anxiety becomes worst. I also experienced trauma upon seeing some news regarding those Indian people who died outside the hospital and burned because of COVID-19. Here in Davao, some hospitals were occupied. That is why I always overthink things that I am going to do to protect myself from any illnesses.

"May time jud nga naka ingon ko, kanus-a pa man intawon ni mahuman uy, kapoy na jud kaayo, pait na jud kaayu, boring na kaayu sa balay, dili pa jud ka kaadto ug simbahan kay utro pud sirado..."

I always ask myself when will this pandemic end. I feel stressed, bored, and sometimes anxious about the thing that is happening today.

5.3. Opportunities for Improvement

PE classes are very helpful during and after the COVID-19 pandemic. The country's higher education commission has mandated all universities and colleges that flexible learning delivery, including blended online, will remain even if in-person classes are allowed. While the participants are generally satisfied with the university's shift to blended online, they have enumerated areas of concern where the school can improve.

"sa PE online classes, teachers should give assignments based on what's available at home. Dapat din iconsider ang changes ng alert level..." Hopefully, mas mapadali ang pag provide ug feedback or comments sa amoang mga submissions kay saying ang time..."

In PE online classes, teachers should give assignments based on what's available at home. Teachers should consider the changes in the alert levels. And hopefully, feedback and comments on our activities will be given abruptly to save time.

"Okay naman ang SIM actually, siguro need lang dungagan ug alternative tasks nga pwede pagpilian namu para maka comply jud mi sa requirements sa PE... Tasks pud nga doable jud labi na sa mga naga rent lang ug room or boarding house lang..."

I don't have a problem regarding the SIM (Self Instructed Manual), maybe the things that should be added are the alternative tasks that

we students can select so that we can comply immediately with the requirement of the PE class. In addition, PE should give also doable activities, especially for those students who are living or renting rooms or boarding houses.

"Unta mas paspas ang pag respond sa help desk sa amoang concerns. I've experienced na nag text ug nag call ko, wala jud ni reply or mutubag man lang, nag sige lang ug ring..."

I hope that the help desk will have an immediate response to our concerns. I have experienced that my calls and texts were rejected.

"Like PE, unta sa ubang subjects mas tagaan pud mi ug enough time to prepare specially sa mga lisud na tasks... few teachers lang man pud ako na experience, kalit lang mag require unya pagka-ugma dayun submit, mabuang jud ko"

"Suggestion, kung pwede nay online tutorials or videos nga ang teachers jud namu ang mag istorya, mas okay jud kung akoang teacher ako makita ug dili mga foreigners... mas ma feel nako ang presence sa teacher kung sila akoa makita sa video..."

I have a suggestion that, if possible, the teacher should provide some tutorial videos. I hope that the teacher himself will have his talk on the video instead of just uploading videos coming from foreigners on YouTube. In that way, I can at least feel his presence.

Online physical education classes are not the same as traditional (face-to-face) physical education classes. The participants had different suggestions for effectively setting up online physical education classes. Such changes are significant for developing and applying group work, which encourages students to participate to overcome the shortcomings of online physical education classes. In the future, new assignments need to be developed to enable teachers to identify the learning status of individual students, just as participants adopt various educational plans to increase the values and purposes of a class.

Conclusion

While the study's results are generally commendable, the study's respondents have raised opportunities for improvement in the university's blended-online delivery. First, the timely provision of quality feedback on students' performance. While this is expected due to the number of PE classes the teacher handle, the PE program may develop auto-generated feedback through personalized analytic rubrics. Second, the respondents have underscored the lack of alternative activities they may choose from, given the limited spaces and equipment at home. The PE program may consider developing a compendium of activities or assessment tasks apart from what is reflected in the module in every course aligned with a specific learning outcome or competency where they choose to suit their context. Third, the respondents strongly prefer seeing their PE teachers in the instructional videos, not foreigners. This can be done through close coordination of the PE program with the ICT and multi-media offices of the university. Lastly, there is a need for the PE program to closely monitor the compliance of teachers with the declared assessment tasks, activities, requirements, and deadlines in the self-instructional module.

While this study has generated positive results relative to the quality of PE teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic, it should not be interpreted as a sweeping general picture of PE teaching and learning. The study is done only in one university system and at the higher education level. The main respondents of the study are the PE students who were asked about the quality of PE teaching and learning; teachers are also worthy of being asked not just about the quality of instruction but also about their struggles during the blended-online delivery mode. The aforesaid limitations are raised to encourage future researchers to conduct an investigation related to this study.

References

- Adedoyin, O. B., & Soykan, E. (2020). Covid-19 pandemic and online learning: the challenges and opportunities. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2020.1813180>
- Andrade, C. (2021). The inconvenient truth about convenience and purposive samples. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 43(1), 86-88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0253717620977>
- Aragon, S. R. (2003). Creating social presence in online environments. In S. R. Aragon (Ed.), *Facilitating learning in online environments* (pp. 57-68). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ace.119>
- Bender, L. (2020). Key messages and actions for COVID-19 prevention and control in schools. <https://www.unicef.org/media/66036/file/Key%20Messages%20and%20Actions%20for%20COV>.
- Biggs, J.B. (2003). *Teaching for quality learning at university*. Buckingham: Open University Press/Society for Research into Higher Education. (Second edition).
- Booker, Q. E., Rebman, C. M. & Kitchens, F.L. (2014) A model for testing technostress in the online education environment: An exploratory study. *Issues in Information Systems* Volume 15, Issue II, pp.214-222. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/fbd0/5663e5be6a4d24dcf624b0aeab2ab524fa3f.pdf>
- Boyer-Davis, S. (2020). Technostress in higher education: An examination of faculty perceptions before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Business and Accounting*, 13(1), 42-58. http://asbbs.org/files/2020/JBA_Vol_13.1_Fall_2020.pdf#page=42

- Chan, W. K., Leung, K. I., Ho, C. C., Wu, C. W., Lam, K. Y., Wong, N., . . . Tse, A. C. Y. (2021). Effectiveness of online teaching in physical education during COVID-19 school closures: A survey study of frontline physical education teachers in hong kong. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 21(4), 1622-1628. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2021.04205>.
- Dhawan, S. (2020). Online learning: A panacea in the time of COVID-19 crisis. *Journal of Educational Technology Systems*, 49, 5-22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0047239520934018>
- Domokos, C., Domokos, M., Mirică, S. N., Negrea, C., Bota, E., & Nagel, A. (2020). Being a student at the faculty of sports and physical education in COVID- 19 pandemic times - A moment in life. *Timisoara Physical Education and Rehabilitation Journal*, 13(24), 45-50. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2478/tperj-2020-0007>.
- Filiz, B., & Konukman, F. (2020). Teaching Strategies for Physical Education during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Editor: Ferman Konukman. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 91(9), 48-50. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07303084.2020.1816099>
- Haig, B.D. (2018). The Philosophy of Quantitative Methods. In: *Method Matters in Psychology. Studies in Applied Philosophy, Epistemology and Rational Ethics*, vol 45. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-01051-5_8
- Hrehorowicz, A. (2021). Sports in college - opinions of generation Z about physical education during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Physical Education and Sport*, 21, 1091-1097. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.7752/jpes.2021.s2137>.
- Hussein, E., Daoud, S., Alrabaiiah, H., & Badawi, R. (2020). Exploring undergraduate students' attitudes towards emergency online learning during COVID-19: A case from the UAE. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105699>
- Jane, C. F., Biswas, S., & Perreira, K. M. (2021). The covid-19 pandemic and mental health of first-year college students: Examining the effect of covid-19 stressors using longitudinal data. *PLoS One*, 16(3) doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0249>.
- Kwang-Jin, L., Noh, B., & Keun-Ok An. (2021). Impact of synchronous online physical education classes using tabata training on adolescents during COVID-19: A randomized controlled study. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(19), 10305. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ijerph181910305>.
- Lau, E. Y. H., & Lee, K. (2020). Parents' views on young children's distance learning and screen time during COVID-19 class suspension in Hong Kong. *Early Education and Development*, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2020.1843925>
- Mocanu, G. D., Murariu, G., Iordan, D. A., Sandu, I., & Mihaela Orlanda, A. M. (2021). The perception of the online teaching process during the COVID-19 pandemic for the students of the physical education and sports domain. *Applied Sciences*, 11(12), 5558. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/app11125558>.
- Nie, Y. (2020). On-line classroom visual tracking and quality evaluation by an advanced feature mining technique. *Signal Processing: Image Communication*, 84, 115817. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.image.2020.115817>
- Pallavi, U., & Vrinda. (2021). Impact of technostress on academic productivity of university students. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(2), 1647-1664. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10639-020-10319-9>
- Pathare, S., Vijayakumar, L., Fernandes, T. N., Shastri, M., Kapoor, A., Pandit, D., Korde, P. (2020). Analysis of news media reports of suicides and attempted suicides during the COVID-19 lockdown in india. *International Journal of Mental Health Systems*, 14, 1-9. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13033-020-00422-2>.
- Pedgley, O., Rognoli, V., & Karana, E. (2016). Materials experience as a foundation for materials and design education. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 26(4), 613-630. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10798-015-9327-y>
- Promoting physical activity during school closures imposed by the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic: Physical education teachers' behaviors in france, italy and turkey. (2020). *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(24), 9431. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17249431>.
- Rodríguez-Moreno, J., Ortiz-Colón, A. M., Córdón-Pozo, E., & Agreda-Montoro, M. (2021). The influence of digital tools and social networks on the digital competence of university students during COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(6), 2835. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18062835>
- Schutt, R. K. (2019). Quantitative methods. *The Wiley Blackwell Companion to Sociology*, 39-56. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119429333.ch3>
- Shakeel, I., & Bhatti, Z. A. (2020). A qualitative exploration of teachers' perspective on smartphones usage in higher education in developing countries: *Revista de universidad y sociedad del conocimiento. International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 17(1) doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s41239-020-00203-4>.
- Shulman, L. (1987). Knowledge and teaching: Foundations of the new reform. *Harvard Educational Review*, 57(1), 1-22.

<https://doi.org/10.17763/haer.57.1.j463w79r56455411>

Spady, W.G. (1988) Organising for results: the basis of authentic restructuring and reform, *Educational Leadership*, October, pp. 4-8. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ378736>

Stein, D. S. (2020). Keeping the promise of distance education: Ethical challenges for higher education administrators. In V. p.-. Wang (Ed.), *Handbook of research on ethical challenges in higher education leadership and administration*. Ohio State: IGI Global. DOI: 10.4018/978-1-7998-4141-8.ch015

Thi, T. T. (2022). Online teaching at the faculty of physical education and sports, Thai Nguyen University of Education, Vietnam: Situations and Solutions. *European Journal of Physical Education and Sports Science*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.46827/ejpe.v8i2.4220>

Thais, J. W. (2020). Distance learning, face to face difficulties: Perspectives in times of COVID-19. *Revista Ibero-Americana De Estudos Em Educação*, 15(4), 1750-1768. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.21723/riaee.v15i4.13761>.

Zhang, W.; Wang, Y.; Yang, L.; Wang, C. (2020). Suspending Classes without Stopping Learning: China's Education Emergency Management Policy in the COVID-19 Outbreak. *Journal of Risk Financial Management*, 13, 55.

Zheng, W., Ma, Y. Y., & Lin, H. L. (2021). Research on blended learning in physical education during the covid-19 pandemic: A case study of chinese students. *SAGE Open*, 11(4), 21582440211058196. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440211058196>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Pedrito M. Castillo II, EdD

University of Mindanao – Philippines

Marmee Rochelle M. Potenciando, EdD

University of Mindanao – Philippines

Glydale John G. Escabarte

University of Mindanao - Philippines